

REFORMS AND MODERN APPROACH IN THE PRESCHOOL EDUCATION SYSTEM

Mo'minova Gulasal Baxodirovna

Teacher of the Kokand State Pedagogical institute

Murotova Mexro'za

Student of the Kokand State Pedagogical institute

Aliyeva Zulxumor

Student of the Kokand State Pedagogical institute

Soxibova Zarnigor

Student of the Kokand State Pedagogical institute

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Annotation. The article analyzes the effectiveness of the work put into practice in the years after the socialization of reforms in the preschool education system in Uzbekistan. The analysis was carried out based on the requirements of the law of the Republic of Uzbekistan " on the mountain of preschool education and upbringing "and the decision of the Republic of Uzbekistan" on approval of the state standard of preschool education and upbringing "No. 802.

Keywords: preschool education, reform, child personality, socialization, educator, upbringing, road map, adaptation, development.

The appropriate maturation of the current young generation, which will decide the day and prospect of our motherland, is connected with the continuous improvement of the educational sphere at the modern level. Expanding the coverage of children with preschool education, further improving the use of preschool education services is the most urgent task before us to provide favorable conditions for their full - fledged life activities and actively engage in social life. "From the moment the child comes into the world, mental activity increases in it precisely at the age of preschool age, moral-aesthetic and physical qualities are formed. Therefore, our strategic goal for the development of the preschool education sector in the coming years is to create the necessary conditions for the full coverage of each child of The Associated age with this education, regardless of their social situation...»[1].

In order to introduce these goals, the Ministry of preschool education of the Republic of Uzbekistan was established in 2017. In the context of changes in the field of education, on the one hand, it is natural that significant changes in all its areas, on the other hand, scientific and technical progress, changes in the nature and content of education require the development of an important and optimal strategy for the development of the field, as well as new approaches and solutions. In this regard, there is also a need to analyze research and predictions in the development of social views in Jamaica, relevant scientific research, such

analyzes can be carried out only on the basis of scientific-critical and creative approaches, relying on deep knowledge and free thoughts. In the age of speed and information, everyday life, forms of interpersonal relationships among people in society are required from everyone, in particular educators, to express their circle to children to mean that it is necessary not only to teach children, but, first of all, to achieve high results and enter into social attitudes, and to reveal their individual abilities.

Ensuring the need for individuals with a creative approach, initiative skills, who can actively and constructively solve contradictions in various spheres that exist in society today is an urgent problem. In order to achieve a solution to the above pressing problem, it is required, first of all, to develop individuality in children, to mature the skills of following national and universal values, criteria and rules. In this, it is mainly advisable to work based on the activities of educators - employees, who are considered an active transformative layer of society. Because only educators-employees, active, creative, enterprising subjects of society, who are considered capable of fulfilling the requirements in our national education, are able to realize such a need. They are required to act based on the basic principle of the unity of education and upbringing, such as encouraging children not only to know universal values, principles, but to express themselves to them and determine their abilities, but also to independently think and operate.

In the implementation of this principle, education and upbringing of the younger generation indicates that in order to achieve a modern level of the system, it is necessary to abandon dogmatic situations that do not meet the requirements of society today. This means that we need to rebound our education on the basis of urgent requirements by abandoning the old methods and introducing new pedagogical technologies into practicality. However, it is necessary to note separately that in the formation of children's consciousness and behavior, overcoming the crisis in the system, we are still meant to rely on the spiritual and cultural heritage left by our great alloms, and the task of transmitting this invaluable heritage to the next generation is meant to the younger generation n our opinion, it will be possible to find a solution to the issue by creating a new system of upbringing and education in such conditions. It is known that in education it will be necessary to determine the basic principles of creating a new one, along with special knowledge, which consciously manages the educational system, without relying solely on values, existing knowledge and social experience. It is worth noting separately that

where the educational system is in crisis, family upbringing is also in crisis there. To prevent this, it will certainly be necessary to update the educational system, to implement effective reforms. At this point, speaking about the scientific basis of the new educational ridge, it is natural that a number of questions arise: can parents act as a leading institution in the education of preschool children? Can a family provide for the upbringing of an active, creative, flexible personality? How is the process of “adaptation” to new conditions and requirements of life taking place in the parents themselves?

From the above it is clear that the most important tasks should be carried out realistically in the field of preschool education only in the period when the educational system is being updated, that is, when education is consciously guided and as a process based on special knowledge. It is required that the quality, content and orientation of preschool education and education be focused on how well they meet the requirements of the Times and that the shortcomings in this regard are quickly eliminated.[3] at this time, it is noticeable that there are cases of an ambiguous perception of childhood and the world of children by adults, and at the same time it is very difficult to get a reasonable answer to the questions of who is the child today, what is his goal, what is the essence of development, who should be him and what It follows from this that, despite the fact that in our eyes there are sufficiently deep ideas about many aspects of human nature, both in the fields of scientific knowledge, such as philosophy, psychology, sociology, pedagogy, these sciences do not have the necessary knowledge in the law of modern human development, in particular in the development of preschool children, it is

In today's updated Uzbekistan, it is becoming more important to carry out work on the basis of modern ideas and concepts in accordance with the era demand of preschool children, educational requirements based on the personality of the child, new curricula, the theory of personality, activity and social structure. The process of development of children, taking into account the content, allows us to get acquainted with the values, criteria, knowledge, forms of behavior, attitudes to everyone as edges of a particular culture, the process of socialization, which we have already mentioned. In this regard, in the even in the reforms of the preschool education system today, the socialization and quality education of the child were considered as the main factors of particular importance is the education of preschool children in Khol, which relies on this factor. The goal further is to build a preschool education system based on

modern requirements. It is worthy of recognition that the material provision of the industry is also provided by the state in this regard.

And the shift in edibility is to raise the educational work of preschool children to a qualitatively new level. It is not an exaggeration to say that the work of always imposing the fate and prosperity of the nation science Marifat began with the systematic maturation of the relationship to life and society in the mind, thinking, behavior of a child, raising a preschool child, initially realizing that preschool education begins. We must educate our children in such a way that they have their own men, be able to socialize quickly to society.

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